

1 From Assemblies to Ancestry: Genomic Advances Illuminates Legume Evolution

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13 Abstract

14 Legumes are diverse, wide-spread and important both ecologically and economically. These

15 features prompted the establishment of hundreds of genome assemblies as resources to investigate

16 key biological questions. In this review, we introduce the reader to the Fabaceae (Leguminosae)

17 family highlighting the importance of this group of plants and its high rates of diversity. The major

18 insights gained from studying its genomic variation are discussed, with focus on whole genome

19 duplications, ancestral chromosome numbers and key biological novelties such as the ability to fix

20 nitrogen through symbiosis with bacteria.

21 Key-words: ancestral karyotype, dysploidy, genome size, polyploidy, WGD - whole genome
22 duplication, whole genome sequencing, repetitive sequences

23

24 **Introduction**

25 The Leguminosae family (Fabaceae) is globally distributed, comprising >22,000 species
26 distributed in >807 genera (POWO, *Plants of the World Online*, 2025), with at least 100 new
27 species being catalogued every year. Members of this family occupy nearly all biomes and exhibit
28 remarkable morphological, ecological, and life-history diversity (Fig. 1). In the last five decades,
29 this diversity was characterized in collections such as the Advances in Legume Systematics series,
30 with the first volume (Polhill and Raven, 1981) published after the international Legume
31 Conference at the Royal Botanic Gardens (Kew, England, July 1978) and the renowned book
32 *Legumes of the World* (Lewis, 2005). More recently, the Legume Data Portal
33 (www.legumedata.org) was created to unify community-endorsed occurrence, taxonomy and
34 phylogenetic data for the family.

35 Legumes provide proteins and other nutrients, benefiting human health (Lewis, 2005;
36 LPWG, *Legume Phylogeny Working Group*, 2013, 2017). Furthermore, due to the remarkable
37 ability of fixing atmospheric nitrogen, legumes have a key role in the development of agriculture
38 and the regulation of ecosystems, since this process enriches soil with nitrogen, reduces the use of
39 synthetic fertilizers and increases yields (Kakraliya *et al.*, 2018; Mathesius, 2022). In addition,
40 legumes can also improve carbon sequestration, enhance nutrient cycling, support crop rotation
41 diversification and emit fewer greenhouse gases per unit area than fertilized non legumes (Stagnari

42 *et al.*, 2017; Mathesius, 2022), underpinning their central roles in agriculture, ecosystem nutrient
43 cycles, and sustainable food systems (Gepts *et al.*, 2005; LPWG, 2017).

44 Legume research began with classical taxonomy studies in the 18th–19th centuries by
45 Augustin Pyrame de Candolle and George Bentham and later progressed through comprehensive
46 morphological treatments and floras into the 20th century (Harms, 1907, 1913; Martin, 1914).
47 From the late 20th century, the use of plastidial and nuclear molecular markers (*rbcL*, *matK* and
48 ITS, the Internal Transcribed Spacer of the 35S rDNA *locus*) reshaped legume systematics, due
49 to, for example, the non-monophyly of the traditional Caesalpinioideae clade, prompting revisions
50 at the genus and higher taxonomic levels (LPWG, 2013; Hughes 2022; Bruneau *et al.*, 2024).
51 During the 1990s–2000s, molecular genetics expanded alongside the rise models for the genomic
52 area, such as *Lotus japonicus* L. and *Medicago trunculata* L. (Handberg and Stougaard, 1992;
53 Barker *et al.*, 1990). Transcriptomes and early genome sequences enabled comparative analyses
54 and translational applications in crop improvement (Gepts *et al.*, 2005; LPWG, 2013).
55 Collaborative efforts, particularly by the Legume Phylogeny Working Group (LPWG), enabled
56 dense plastid (*matK*) and multilocus sampling to generate a nearly complete family-level
57 phylogeny (LPWG, 2013, 2017). More recently, phylogenomics applying target-capture DNA
58 sequencing and transcriptomic data have expanded sampling including herbarium materials,
59 making possible a better understanding of the evolution of the family (Koenen *et al.*, 2020). Also,
60 the advances in sequencing technologies in the last decades is providing reference genome
61 assemblies that, associated with integrative bioinformatic approaches, have the potential to solve
62 multiple questions (Satam *et al.*, 2023).

63 The recent, large-scale phylogenetic studies have shown that the traditional three-
64 subfamily classification does not reflect the evolutionary history of legumes. In particular, the
65 traditional Caesalpinioideae was found to be paraphyletic, leading to a reclassification into six
66 monophyletic subfamilies: Cercidoideae, Detarioideae, Duparquetioideae, Dialioideae, a
67 recircumscribed Caesalpinioideae (including the Mimosoid clade), and Papilionoideae (LPWG,
68 2017). The Papilionoideae subfamily is the largest clade in Leguminosae and concentrates almost
69 all economically important crops of the family, including soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.],
70 common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.), pea (*Pisum sativum* L.), chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.),
71 lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.), and peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.).

72 With this robust phylogenetic framework as background, this review synthesizes current
73 advances in legume genomics, with emphasis on its contribution to the understanding of legumes
74 evolution. We discuss the genomic variation observed in the family, the efforts undertaken so far
75 for making complete reference genome assemblies available, the synteny relationships between
76 these available genomes and the efforts towards the reconstruction of an ancestral genome. We
77 also discuss the contribution of these advances for central questions of legume plant biology, such
78 as the ability to nodulate.

79

80 **Legumes diversification and genomic variation**

81 One of the main evolutionary questions related to legumes is to understand the high rates
82 of diversification of the group, considered the third largest family of flowering plants, only after
83 Asteraceae and Orchidaceae. The group counts with a great collection of fossil records, mostly
84 dated from ~65.3 Mya during the Paleocene, right after the Cretaceous–Paleogene (K–Pg) mass

85 extinction event caused by the impact of an asteroid on the coast of Mexico. These sources of
86 evidence helped to propose a dated calibrated phylogenetic scenario, revealing that legumes passed
87 through a rapid diversification and spreading across the continents marked by complex
88 paleopolyploid (or ancient whole genome duplication - WGD) events, with at least six (close to
89 the K/Pg boundary) occurring at the Leguminosae ancestor or in one of the subfamilies, which
90 probably influenced the survival and evolution of the group (Koenen *et al.*, 2021; Zhao *et al.*,
91 2021). Most legume species are distributed in the tropical regions of the globe, and the temperate
92 species are hypothesized to have colonized this region only after the transition from wood to
93 herbaceous growth form. What is a consensus is that repeated diversification events occurred
94 during the evolution of the group, with recent radiations as the ones observed in the genera *Lupinus*
95 (*Nevado et al.*, 2016) and *Inga* (*Schley et al.*, 2025).

96 Although the diversity of the Leguminosae family have been investigated during the last
97 years, there are remaining questions about its species inventory, geographical distribution and
98 evolutionary relationships. Fernandes *et al.* (2025) analysed the gaps in these fields and estimated
99 that at least 11% (around 2505 species) of the diversity of legumes are yet not described, which is
100 consistent with the prediction that 10-20% of the vascular plant species are unknown (*Joppa et al.*,
101 2011). The understanding of spatial distribution of at least 20% of the accepted legume species is
102 compromised by the lack of geographic data; and at least 50% of all legumes miss DNA
103 sequencing data, even for well-known molecular markers such as ITS, *matK*, *psbA*, *rbcL* and *trnL*,
104 hampering a complete phylogenetic analysis of legumes evolutionary history.

105 The high rates of legume diversity are also reflected in the genomic variation present in the
106 family. The analysis of chromosome number and ploidy level by cytogenetic and genomic
107 approaches has helped to shed light onto this variation. Legumes vary in chromosome numbers

108 from $2n = 12$ (as in *Sesbania bispinosa* (Jacq.) W.Wight) to $2n = 208$ (as in *Vachellia hebeclada*
109 (DC.) Kyal. & Boatwr.; Bairiganjan and Patinaik, 1989; Santos *et al.*, 2025). Variations in
110 chromosome numbers are associated to events of polyploidy (such as $n = 21, 28, 56$) and dysploidy,
111 meaning changes in chromosome number due to chromosomal structural rearrangements (such as
112 $n = 11, 12, 13$) (Cordeiro and Felix, 2017). Polyploidy occurred several times during the evolution
113 of legumes, since their origin to recent lineages as in soybean, and it is pointed as a key drive of
114 its diversification (Doyle, 2012).

115 For decades, the analysis of chromosome number was the only source of information for
116 the study of karyotype evolution of legumes. Goldblatt (1981) highlighted polyploidy and
117 aneuploidy (possibly meaning dysploidy) cases across different groups of legumes and estimated
118 the basic chromosome number $x = 7$ for the family, which became $x = 14$ in the Papilionoideae
119 subfamily due to an ancient polyploid event. Subsequent chromosome reductions led to $x = 6, 7,$
120 $8, 9, 10$ and 11 for different groups within Papilionoideae. The basic number $x = 7$ proposed for
121 Leguminosae was later endorsed by analyses of chromosome counts in the light of phylogenetic
122 reconstruction, which calculated the modal gametic chromosomal count for Cercidoideae as $n =$
123 $7, 14$, Detarioideae as $n = 12$, Dialioideae as $n = 14$, and Caesalpinioideae as $n = 12-14$, with 13
124 for the Mimosoid clade. In Papilionoideae, the early-branching Papilionoideae lineages showed n
125 $= 13-14$, while other groups varied from 7 to 11 , as genistoids (9), dalbergioids (10), baphioids
126 (11), mirbelioids ($7-9$), Robineae ($10-11$), Loteae ($6-8$), the IRLC clade ($7, 8$), indigoferoid ($7, 8$)
127 and millettoid (11) (Stai *et al.*, 2019). In this scenario, at least five WGD events influenced the
128 chromosome number in the family: in Cercidoideae, Detarioideae, Dialioideae, Caesalpinioideae
129 and Papilionoideae (Stai *et al.*, 2019). These WGD events were also supported by a broader
130 phylotranscriptomic and phylogenomic analysis, but an additional WGD event at the base of

131 Leguminosae was also postulated, as well as more recent duplications and triplications in a total
132 of 28 WGD//WGT events in the family (Zhao *et al.*, 2021). This additional WGD shared by all
133 legumes is controversial. It was also dated to the K/Pg boundary, as the subfamily-specific WGD
134 events, and would imply, for instance, a basic number of $x = 28$ for Papilionoideae, what is not
135 supported for by other evidence.

136 A recent large-scale cytogenetic analysis of Caesalpinioideae species (Santos *et al.*, 2025)
137 highlighted the remarkable variation in chromosome number, heterochromatin organization, and
138 genome size within the subfamily. Despite the wide range in chromosome numbers—from $2n =$
139 14 to $2n = 208$ —the most common number across the clade are $2n = 26$ and 28. Based on a
140 phylogenetic framework, which suggested a diversification time of approximately 64.3 Mya for
141 the subfamily, the authors reconstructed a basic chromosome number of $x = 14$. The results
142 indicated that polyploidization, followed by both ascending and descending dysploidy, has been
143 the primary driver of karyotype evolution in Caesalpinioideae.

144 Another way of accessing the genomic variation in plants is through the estimation of their
145 genome size by techniques such as flow cytometry. Genome size estimations can capture the large
146 existent variation among plants, which ranges from 0.59 Gbp/1C in the carnivorous plant *Genlisea*
147 *tuberosa* Rivadavia, Gonella & A. Fleischm (Fleischmann *et al.*, 2014) to 160.45 Gbp/1C in the
148 Caledonian fork fern (*Tmesipteris oblanceolate* Copel.) (Fernández *et al.*, 2024). For legumes,
149 according to the Plant DNA C- values database provided by the Kew Botanic Garden
150 (<https://cvalues.science.kew.org/>), the DNA amount can vary in from 1C = 0.28 picograms (1C =
151 274 Mbp) in *Lotus unifoliolatus* to 1C = 27.40 pg (1C = 26.8 Gbp) in *Vicia faba*, a 97-fold
152 variation. This variation in size can be explained by polyploidy and by the differential

153 accumulation of the repetitive fraction, mostly by the expansion of specific satellite DNAs or
154 different lineages of retroelements, as the Ty1/copia and Ty3/gypsy LTR-retrotransposons (Macas
155 *et al.*, 2015; Vicient and Casacuberta, 2017).

156 Whole-genome duplications (WGDs), or polyploidy events, are widespread in plants and
157 other eukaryotes. By generating duplicated genetic material—genes and regulatory components—
158 they enhance evolutionary potential and enable novel traits and innovations. WGDs can also
159 provide short-term advantages such as stress tolerance, heterozygosity, and shifts toward selfing
160 or asexuality, which may aid survival during environmental change (Van de Peer *et al.*, 2009;
161 Clark and Donoghue, 2018). In the evolutionary history of legumes, the existence of WGDs events
162 has also helped to shape its variation in genome size and karyotype evolution. Genomic data have
163 proposed an ancient papilionoid WGD (59 Mya), retained as paralogous blocks in many legume
164 genomes (e.g., soybean, *Medicago*, chickpea), and a more recent, lineage-specific *Glycine max*
165 (soybean) WGD (13 Mya), that doubled soybean gene content and produced widespread retained
166 duplicates and fractionation, the loss of duplicate genes after whole genome duplication (Schmutz
167 *et al.*, 2010; Young *et al.*, 2011). Other Papilionoideae, such as *Cajanus cajan* (L.) Huth (pigeon
168 pea), lack a recent WGD but still show synteny in WGD-derived regions (Varshney *et al.*, 2012).
169 These ancient WGD signatures are also present in other genomes (e.g., lentil, chickpea, cowpea)
170 as residual paralogous blocks and elevated duplicate fractions (Varshney *et al.*, 2013; Lonardi *et*
171 *al.*, 2019; Ramsay *et al.*, 2021). Allotetraploid crops such as cultivated peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*
172 L.) experienced hybrid polyploidy, producing A and B subgenomes with homeolog pairs showing
173 biased retention, subgenome dominance and differential expression (Zhuang *et al.*, 2019).

174 Although there are multiple evidences of WGD in Leguminosae, two factors limit the
175 discussion about the time of these events and whether they are shared or not among lineages: the

176 small and limited number of genome assemblies available for the other subfamilies, except
177 Papilionoideae, and the lacking of discussion about genome evolution in most part of the papers
178 published, with some being restricted to the description of the assembly or focused in functional
179 properties. As an example, for the Cercidoideae subfamily, only 4 genomes are currently available,
180 the genomes for *Cercis canadensis* and *C. chuniana* (Griesmann et al., 2018; Gong et al., 2025),
181 *Bauhinia variegata* (Zhong et al., 2022) and the marama bean (*Tylosema esculentum*) (Li and
182 Cullis, 2025). For *Cercis* species, the first genome is focused on the evolution of nodulation, while
183 the more recent one only describes the assembly for *C. chuniana*, with no discussion. In the
184 genome description of *Bauhinia variegata*, a comparison is made with the *C. canadensis* genome,
185 revealing the presence of signatures for a specific WGD in *Bauhinia*. For the marama bean genome
186 study, it was compared in the synteny level only with *B. variegata*, displaying several breaks of
187 synteny (mostly inversions and translocations), while *Ks* analysis suggested that the species
188 probably underwent multiple rounds of WGD, which could explain the complexity of its genome.

189

190 **Genomic resources and their contributions to deciphering legume genomic evolution**

191 According to the NCBI genome platform (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/genome), when
192 considering only scaffold (S) and chromosome (C) scale genome assemblies at the time of writing,
193 over 350 genome assemblies are publicly available for Leguminosae, which represents around 75
194 genera, covering all subfamilies except Duparquetioideae. These include Papilionoideae (54
195 genera, 317 assemblies, S=83, C=237), Caesalpinioideae (15 genera, 28 assemblies, S=14, C=14),
196 Detarioideae (2 genera, 2 assemblies, S=1, C=1), Cercidoideae (3 genera, 4 assemblies, S=2, C=2),
197 and Dialioideae (2 genera, 2 assemblies, S=1, C=1). When analysing the PubPlant database

198 (https://www.plabipd.de/pubplant_main.html Schwacke *et al.*, 2025), which unifies only the
199 genome assemblies associated with a formal publication, Papilionoideae still concentrates most
200 studies (around 124 assemblies), followed by Caesalpinioideae with 23 assemblies, Cercidoideae
201 (8), Dialioideae (2) and Detarioideae (1). This source does not differentiate the scale of the
202 assemblies, including assemblies composed only by contigs. Although genome assemblies at
203 scaffold level are important, especially in studies of genes, here we focus the discussion mainly in
204 assemblies at chromosome scale and its use in the analysis of the genomic evolution of the family
205 and subfamilies.

206 The legume genomic era started with the draft genome assemblies for the model species
207 *Lotus japonicus* and *Medicago truncatula*. *Lotus japonicus* is a widespread early-flowering plant
208 ($2n = 12$), from the same genus as the polyploid *Lotus corniculatus*, a temperate forage, that has
209 been used worldwide by scientists as a legume model, especially on the study of the mechanisms
210 associated with nodulation (Ferreira and Pedrosa-Harand, 2014). The first genome assembly for
211 the species was based in shotgun and clone-to-clone using BACs (Bacterial Artificial
212 Chromosomes) and TACs (Transformation-competent Artificial Chromosomes) sequencing
213 technologies, producing 44,464 contigs and approaching 315 Mbp of genome sequences,
214 corresponding to ~67% of the total genome size previously estimated (475 Mb) and covering ~91%
215 of the gene content (Sato *et al.*, 2008). Despite limited in coverage, this first version of the genome
216 has brought to light important features as the identification of specific genes, its incompleteness
217 and the scarcity of other legume genomes, limiting deeper analysis on the evolution of the family.
218 More recently, a high quality genome assembly using an association of Illumina, Pac-Bio and Hi-
219 C (chromatin conformation) data has been published for *L. japonicus*, providing a more complete
220 chromosome scale version with 544 Mb in size (357 Mb being repeats) and 27,911 annotated

221 genes, making possible more accurate analysis and the comparison to more legume assemblies
222 available as *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Vigna radiata*, *Vigna angularis*, *Glycine max* and *Cicer arietinum*
223 (Li *et al.*, 2020).

224 *Medicago truncatula* has been chosen as a model legume mostly due to its fast vegetative
225 growth, small diploid genome size (different from its close related crop *M. sativa*, which is a
226 tetraploid) and its low requirement for cultivation factors as temperature and light. The first draft
227 genome for *Medicago truncatula* was released by Young *et al.* (2011), also based on conventional
228 cloning approach using BACs followed by shotgun sequencing, capturing ~94% of *M. truncatula*
229 genes. During the following years this version passed through improvements, with new releases
230 being published in 2014 (Tang *et al.*, 2014) and 2018 (Pecrix *et al.*, 2018). This last one is the most
231 recent version, which was generated through Pac-Bio long read sequencing approach,
232 accomplishing high levels of completeness and making possible to identify rearrangements in
233 base-pair resolution among different genotypes.

234 Among other legume genomes assemblies available so far, the majority belongs to the
235 Papilionoideae family, mainly focusing on economic important crops such as soyabean (*Glycine*
236 *max* L.), common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.), cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.], chickpea
237 (*Cicer arietinum* L.), lentil (*Lens* spp.) and peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). The soybean genome
238 (~1.1 Gb in size and ~46,430 genes annotated) was one of the first reference genome for legumes
239 and helped to evidence two WGD events, an ancient one in the Papilionoideae clade and a specific
240 one in *Glycine max* lineage, occurring ~56.5 and ~10 million years ago, respectively. Extensive
241 paralog retention, and gene-fractionation patterns critical for trait mapping and polyploid evolution
242 were reported (Schmutz *et al.*, 2010). The draft genome assembly for chickpea (~738 Mb in size,

243 ~28,269 genes annotated) provided a catalogue for resistance genes to many plant pests and
244 pathogens and identified SNPs (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) and SSRs (Simple Sequence
245 Repeats) markers with potential to support genomic breeding in this orphan crop. When compared
246 to other legume genomes available at that time, as *M. truncatula*, *L. japonicus*, pigeon pea
247 [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Huth] and soybean, chickpea presented an extensive conservation of synteny
248 (around 90%) (Varshney et al., 2013).

249 The common bean reference genome assembly (~474 Mb in size) enabled synteny analysis
250 with the previous soybean genome. Both species diverged ~19.2 Mya and evidence suggest that,
251 after the split, *P. vulgaris* evolved faster than *G. max*. When comparing the synteny of both
252 genomes, most of the ortholog genes between the species were syntenic, except for the
253 pericentromeric regions, which presented breaks of microcolinearity. Due to the specific WGD in
254 soybean, most of the genomic blocks in the common bean could be found twice in soybean
255 genome, and the presence of more than 90% of *P. vulgaris* genes in *G. max* is probably a result of
256 the shared ancient WGD. Additionally, the analysis of the common bean genome assembly
257 revealed distinct selective sweeps for the two pools of diversification (Mesoamerican vs. Andean)
258 associated with the two events of domestication and provided specific regions of the genome that
259 can be used in the future studies as targets to crop improvement (Schmutz *et al.*, 2014). In addition,
260 a reference genome was assembled for cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), with the identification of
261 ~29,773 protein-coding loci and candidate genes responsible for the process of domestication and
262 the control of organ size (Lonardi *et al.*, 2019).

263 Chromosome-scale assemblies for cultivated and wild lentils (*Lens culinaris*, ~3.8 Gb,
264 ~39,778 genes; *L. ervoides*, ~2.9 Gb, ~37,045 genes) revealed repeat expansion, structural

265 rearrangements, and insights for introgression breeding (Ramsay *et al.*, 2021). And the
266 allotetraploid peanut (*Arachis hypogea*, $2n = 4x = 40$) haplotype resolved genome assembly (~2.5
267 Gb, ~83,709 genes) characterized its A and B subgenomes, shedding light on homeolog dynamics,
268 resistance-gene repertoires, and domestication-related gene-family changes (Zhuang *et al.*, 2019).
269 A reference genome assembly, although not at chromosome-scale, was generated for *Stylosanthes*
270 *scabra* ($2n = 4x = 40$), a relative of peanut which is an orphan legume from the Caatinga biome in
271 Brazil, a region characterized by its long dry season. The analysis of the genome identified 22,681
272 protein-coding genes that corresponded to 41% of the genome content and the authors discuss the
273 role of specific genes in the adaptation of the plant to the environment, especially genes associated
274 with resistance to pathogens and to drought (Ferreira-Neto *et al.*, 2023).

275 The first pea (*Pisum sativum*; $2n=14$) reference genome (Kreplak *et al.*, 2019) was a great
276 advance in the genomic era for legumes, especially considering the challenge of sequencing and
277 assembling genomes with a large size ($1C = \sim 4.5$ Gbp) and for its importance as the first model
278 plant studied by Gregor Mendel. Approximately 44,756 genes were identified and annotated,
279 however the largest fraction of the genome (~83%) has found to be composed of repetitive
280 elements, in particular long terminal repeats (LTR) retrotransposons, estimated to be the main
281 source of genome size expansion in the species due to the ability of these retrotransposons self-
282 copying and move across the genome. The author also brought evidence that suggests a higher rate
283 of genomic evolution in comparison with other legumes. More recently, an improved reference
284 genome was proposed for pea (Yang *et al.*, 2022), with larger contiguity specially for the repetitive
285 regions but also bringing to light insights about the function of genes postulated more than one
286 century ago by Mendel, mostly related to seed shape and stem length. Another legume with a giant
287 genome is Faba bean [*Vicia faba* L. ($2n=12$)], with a genome size three times higher than pea (~13

288 Gbp). A reference genome for the species has also been recently assembled (Jayakodi *et al.*, 2023),
289 and the size variation could not be explained by any recent WGD event in *V. faba*. A deeper
290 investigation of its repetitive fraction revealed that, similarly to pea, the faba bean genome passed
291 through multiple expansions promoted by LTR-retrotransposons and tandem repeats (satellite
292 DNAs), specially from the Ty3-gypsy-Ogre family, that alone comprised 44% of the total genome
293 size and a diverse number of satellite tandem repeats (9.4%), mostly distributed at the
294 pericentromeres.

295 The other subfamilies of Leguminosae are less represented in genomic efforts. The
296 Caesalpinioideae subfamily counts with only 28 genome assemblies available so far (scaffold or
297 chromosome scale), representing only 9% (15) of the 165 genera described for the clade. Among
298 those, we can highlight the genome assembly of *Senna tora*, which is widely used by its medicinal
299 properties (Kang *et al.*, 2020). Specific gene families related to the anthraquinone biosynthesis
300 were identified, and it constitutes the first reference genome for the genus *Senna*, which is marked
301 by polyploidy and dysploidy events.

302 Similar efforts have recently provided haplotype resolved chromosome-scale genome
303 assemblies for seven genomes of economically important trees from Caesalpinioideae subfamily
304 (including species from the Mimosoideae clade) as *Acacia confusa* (566 Mbp), *Delonix regia* (580
305 Mbp), *Mimosa bimucronata* (641 Mbp), *Albizia julibrissin* (705 Mbp), *Biancaea sappan* (872
306 Mbp), *Gleditsia sinensis* (921 Mbp) and *Leucaena leucocephala* (1.3 Gbp) and further comparison
307 analysis that helped to bring insights about the polyploidization history of the group (Chen *et al.*,
308 2024). The authors identified and discussed that after the WGD event shared by all
309 Caesalpinioideae around 72 Mya, additional two recent events (16.2–19.5 and 7.1–9.5 Mya)

310 happened in *L. leucocephala*, which was characterized as an octoploid ($2n = 8x = 112$) that passed
311 through gene loss (~40%) and contractions of its genome size, mainly promoted by diploidization
312 processes. Also, a larger scale phylogenomic analysis with more seven available genome
313 assemblies suggests that the species belonging to the Mimosoideae clade have evolved faster than
314 remaining species from Caesalpinioideae. Since the basic number proposed for Mimosoideae clade
315 and most species of Caesalpinioideae is $x = 13$ or 14 , the authors analysed the macrosynteny among
316 species. The results revealed that species with $n = 13$ diverged later in comparison to the species
317 with $n = 14$ and the chromosome structure appeared to be more conserved among Mimosoid than
318 in remaining Caesalpinioideae. More interestingly, the authors identified two chromosomes in
319 species with $n = 14$ that fused to one chromosome in the karyotype with $n = 13$. Other genome
320 assemblies are being generated for the subfamily, as the first genome assemblies for *Inga Inga*
321 *leyocalycina* and *Inga laurina*; Schley *et al.*, 2024) and *Acacia* (*Acacia pycnantha*; McLay *et al.*,
322 2022), this last one considered the largest plant genus spread in Australia. Although, according to
323 the PubPlant platform, *Acacia* is the genus with more genome assemblies available for
324 Caesalpinioideae (at least 5), there is still not a wide genomic comparison for the genus, which
325 should be a target for future studies.

326 When we consider the other subfamilies, Detarioideae has only one genome assembly
327 available at scaffold scale, corresponding to less than 1% of the species diversity already described
328 for the clade. The available assembly is for *Eurypetalum unijugum*, however the genome is not
329 associated to a formal published study. In Cercidoideae, only four genome assemblies are available
330 so far at the NCBI databank (also less than 1% of the species described), in scaffold or chromosome
331 scale. According to the PubPlant database, four further genomes are published, but ed at contig
332 scale. Among those assemblies, the majority is for species belonging to *Cercis* (3) and *Bauhinia*

333 (3). In *Cercis*, the species analysed so far were *C. canadensis*, *C. chinensis* and *C. chuniana*
334 (Griesmann *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2023; Gong *et al.*, 2025), however two of these studies limited
335 the discussion to the genomic evolution of the genus or the subfamily, focusing on the description
336 of the assembly or in the genes related to nodulation. The genome of *C. chinensis* brings evidence
337 that the species did not undergo polyploidization events, in comparison of gene orders among *C.*
338 *chinensis*, soybean and coffee. These results argue against a legume wide WGD event, which were
339 thus restricted to each subfamily.

340 For the *Bauhinia* genus, the three species with genome assemblies available so far are *B.*
341 *variegata*, *B. purpurea* and the hybrid between both species, the Hong Kong orchid tree *Bauhinia*
342 *×blakeana* Dunn (Zhong *et al.*, 2022; Mu *et al.*, 2025), this last one being one of the most complete
343 genomes assemblies phased by haplotype and telomere-to-telomere. In the more recent study, the
344 *Bauhinia* species are compared in the genomic context with other legumes (including *Cercis* and
345 model species as soybean, *L. japonicus* and *M. truncatula*), however only in the context of retraction
346 and expansion of the specific genes (especially the ones related to resistance and terpene
347 synthesis). The other two genomes for Cercidoideae, are the haplotype phased genome of *Phanera*
348 *championii* (Lu *et al.*, 2024) and for the marama bean (*Tylosema esculentum*; Li and Cullis, 2025).
349 The comparative genomics of *P. championii*, mostly with species from Papilionoideae clade,
350 revealed that the species experienced two WGD events, with ~59.6% of its genes originating after
351 these events. The marama bean genome analysis indicated a phylogenetic proximity of the species
352 with *Cercis* and *Bauhinia*, plus an ancient duplication event.

353 In Dialioideae, the two genome assemblies available represent two of the 17 genera
354 described for the subfamily, corresponding to only ~2.3% of the 86 described species. Among the

355 assemblies, only one is at chromosome scale, from *Zenia insignis* (Chen *et al.*, 2025), but it focuses
356 at the description of the assembly. For *Dycorinia guianensis*, the scaffolds are phased with one
357 assembly to each of its haplotypes (Schmitt *et al.*, 2024) and the focus of the study is the
358 transmission of low-frequency mutation. The Duparquetioideae subfamily is a special case, since
359 it is composed by only one species (*Duparquetia orchidacea*), which is sister to the remaining
360 legumes. The genome organization of *Duparquetia* could give important insights into the evolution
361 and diversification of the family. However, no genome assembly was generated so far and even
362 general genetic information as genome content (1C value) or chromosome number are inexistent
363 for the species

364 With the advance of sequencing technologies in the recent years, allied to the decrease of
365 their prices, it is expected an increase of the number of available genome assemblies in the
366 following years. Long read sequencing technologies as PacBio HiFi associated or not with Hi-C
367 data and Oxford Nanopore (ONT) have revolutionized genomics through the facilitation to
368 generate high quality assemblies (Athanasopoulou *et al.*, 2021; Mardis *et al.*, 2025), making
369 available telomere to telomere (T2T) and haplotype phased reference genomes, as the one provided
370 for the Hong Kong orchid tree *Bauhinia ×blakeana* (Cercidoideae) (Mu *et al.*, 2025), and for
371 model or economically important species from Papilionoideae subfamily as *M. truncatula* (Shen
372 *et al.*, 2025), soybean (accession ZH13; Zhang *et al.*, 2023), common bean (*P. vulgaris* YP4; Wang
373 *et al.*, 2025) and cultivated peanut (Wang *et al.*, 2025).

374 **Synteny and Ancestral genomes**

375 Papilionoid, by far the largest subfamily, has been the mostly investigated so far, with most
376 of the genome assemblies distributed among the tribes Phaseoleae, Dalbergieae, Robinieae and in

377 species belonging to the clade with a loss of the chloroplast inverted repeat region (IRLC- Inverted
378 Repeat-Lacking Clade, included in Papilionoideae). The reconstruction of ancestral genomes for
379 the tribes, subfamily and family is still a big challenge, especially because plant genomes are prone
380 to events as whole genome duplications (WGD) followed by diploidization involving structural
381 rearrangements such as inversions, duplications, translocation, fusions and fissions.

382 Ren et al. (2019) proposed an ancestral genome for legumes based syntenic blocks of
383 selected legumes with genome assemblies available (*Arachis duranensis*, *A. ipaensis*, *C. cajan*, *G.*
384 *max*, *P. vulgaris*, *Vigna radiata*, *L. japonicus*, *M. truncatula* and *C. arietinum*). The authors
385 discussed that the most recent common ancestor of the Papilionoideae probably had a haploid
386 karyotype with nine chromosomes ($x = 9$). In this scenario, a putative single fusion reduced the
387 chromosome number from $n = 9$ to 8 in *M. truncatula* and *C. arietinum*, diverse structural
388 rearrangements reduced this number to $n = 6$ in *L. japonicus*, and fissions increased chromosome
389 number to $n = 10$ and then to $n = 11$ in *Phaseolus* and *Vigna* species. Due to the particular WGD
390 event that occurred around 10 Mya in *Glycine*, this number was doubled to $n = 20$. Considering
391 the base chromosome number for the Leguminosae family as $x = 7$ (Goldblatt, 1981; Doyle, 2012),
392 the haploid chromosome number $n = 14$ proposed for the early diverged papilionoid is a result of
393 the WGD event, with $n = 9$ being an intermediate stage during the diversification of the group.

394 To investigate the genome evolution of specific-clades or species, different ancestral
395 genome predictions have been made in recent years. The analysis of the white lupin (*Lupinus albus*
396 L.) genome in comparison to others 11 legume genomes predicted an ancestral legume karyotype
397 composed of 16 conserved regions instead of only 14, although two putative chromosomes were
398 marked small (Hufnagel et al., 2020). The authors hypothesised that during the evolution of the

399 white lupin genome, 15 chromosome fissions and 21 fusions resulted in the lupin ancestor with n
400 = 9. The last experienced a whole genome triplication to result in the intermediate ancestral
401 karyotype with $n = 27$. The establishment of the reference genome for pea (Kreplak *et al.*, 2019)
402 provided hypotheses for ancestral genomes for the family and for the Galegoid (pea, lentils,
403 chickpea and faba bean) and Milletoid (common bean, cowpea and mung bean) clades through
404 synteny analysis. These two clade-specific ancestral genomes, with $n = 8$ and $n = 16$, respectively,
405 were proposed based on an ancestral legume karyotype with 25 synteny blocks arranged in 19
406 proto-chromosomes, higher than the putative $x = 14$ after WGD. The pea genome revealed specific
407 breaks of synteny, usually associated to 5S rDNA sites, suggesting a role of this ribosomal DNA
408 in these translocation events.

409 The analysis of the peanut reference genome also supported the prediction of an ancestral
410 legume karyotype, based on the genes of common bean corresponding to 16 pseudo-molecules.
411 The comparison with this ancestral genome was used to unveil the evolutionary pathway of peanut
412 karyotype. Six peanuts' chromosomes originated from six fusions of twelve ancestral
413 chromosomes, while the remaining four chromosomes were generated by two translocations
414 among ancestral chromosomes. A and B subgenomes were later differentiated by translocation
415 involving B7 and B8 (Zhuang *et al.*, 2019).

416 In order to investigate the chromosome evolution and propose an ancestral genome for the
417 tribe Phaseoleae, Montenegro *et al.* (2022) used a genomic block approach and hypothesized an
418 Ancestral Phaseoleae Karyotype (APK) with $n = 11$ as a result from five end-to-end fusions of the
419 16 putative ancestral chromosomes proposed by Hufnagel *et al.* (2020), involving the two smallest
420 blocks mentioned above, and in accordance with the previous basic chromosome number described

421 to species belonging to this tribe (Ren *et al.* 2019). This analysis identified recurrent centromere
422 repositioning events, particularly in common bean (*P. vulgaris* L.). More efforts are necessary to
423 elucidate the ancestral karyotype of Leguminosae, since most chromosome scale assemblies
424 available so far are provided only to the Papilionoideae subfamily and not even its putative 14
425 ancestral chromosomes are elucidated.

426

427 **Legumes Biology: Nodulation**

428 Legumes are well-known for their ability of forming a symbiotic complex with
429 diazotrophic (capable of nitrogen fixing) bacteria, that are generally referred to as rhizobia, or with
430 bacteria from the genus *Frankia*. These bacteria concentrate their activities inside of specialized
431 structures located in the roots called nodules. Fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) occurs by the
432 action of nitrogenase enzyme that catalyses nitrogen molecules into ammonia (NH₃), which can
433 be processed by the plant during photosynthesis (Sprent, 2009). This important trait was identified
434 during the 19th century, firstly with the description of rhizobia and then *Frankia* activities
435 (Hellriegel and Wilfarth, 1888; Hiltner, 1895), opening the discussion about the scattered and
436 restricted distribution of nodulation among flowering plants. The mechanisms of infection used by
437 N-fixing bacteria are diverse and the structures formed in the roots and nodules also vary (Xu and
438 Wang, 2023).

439 Nodulation seems to have evolved independently in different clades during evolution. The
440 distribution of nodulating plants across the phylogeny shows that nodulating and non-nodulating
441 lineages are grouped in a monophyletic clade that comprises representants of the Fabales, Fagales,
442 Cucurbitales and Rosales orders, referred as the nitrogen-fixing clade (Soltis *et al.*, 1995). Among

443 the six legume subfamilies, the species within Cercidoideae, Detarioideae, Dialioideae and
444 Duparquetioideae are considered as non-nodulating, restricting the nodulation to a single
445 Papilionoideae+Caesalpinioideae clade (Ardley and Sprent, 2021). But the non-legume lineage
446 *Parasponia* from the Cannabaceae (Rosales) family, for instance, is also capable of hosting
447 rhizobia bacteria and processing atmospheric nitrogen (Behm *et al.*, 2014).

448 The evolutionary origins of nodulation are still uncertain and in constant debate. To explain
449 the interspersed distribution of both lineages, the most accepted hypothesis is that this character
450 evolved through parallel evolution followed by successive losses by selection pressure (Griesmann
451 *et al.*, 2018; van Velzen *et al.*, 2018, 2019; Zhao *et al.*, 2021). However this hypothesis is still in
452 debate, especially considering two aspects: parallel evolution itself cannot explain why all
453 nodulating species are situated in the nitrogen-fixing clade without considering a common ancestor
454 ~100 My that facilitated the process (Soltis *et al.*, 1995; Werner *et al.*, 2014), and also the conflict
455 between several parallel origins and data about structure and development of nodulation (Swensen,
456 1996; van Velzen *et al.*, 2019).

457 The use of third generation sequencing technologies allied to transcriptomic data has
458 increased the understanding of the mechanisms behind the evolution and function of nodulation.
459 For example, the genome assembly for *Astragalus sinicus* and data about the expression of its
460 genes revealed expansion of specific genes related to resistance and its primarily accumulation on
461 the roots, enhancing roots protection during symbiosis (Chang *et al.*, 2022). The improved version
462 of the genome assembly of the model *Medicago truncatula* by PacBio sequencing and tissue-
463 specific (roots and nodules) RNA sequencing promoted a better understanding of the genetic
464 regulation of nodulation, characterizing the involvement of long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) in

465 the symbiosis, plus the organization of the nodule expressed genes in genomic clusters (named by
466 the author as symbiotic islands), which can be regulated by DNA methylation (Pecrix *et al.*, 2018).

467 More recently, using extensive phylogenomic (88 species) and phylotranscriptomic (151
468 RNA-seq libraries) approaches, Zhang *et al.* (2024) provided an overview of the genetics of
469 nitrogen-fixing root-nodule symbiosis. The authors found no evidence that individual genes
470 evolved through convergence. Approximately 70% of the symbiosis-related genes identified were
471 conserved across the species analysed, with particular attention given to the NIN gene, which has
472 a unique role in nodulation. NIN is considered the best candidate gene specifically associated with
473 nodulation and warrants further investigation. The study also raised the possibility that
474 intermediate species may exist between nodulating and non-nodulating plants—species that
475 possess only part of the genetic machinery required for nodulation. However, confirming this will
476 require either identifying such species in nature or engineering them experimentally. Although
477 these findings provide new insights into the evolution of nodulation, the question of its origin
478 remains unresolved. This is particularly challenging given that nodulation fulfils similar functions
479 in species that diverged more than 100 million years ago, despite involving different bacterial
480 partners and structures. To test competing hypotheses—whether nodulation originated once from
481 an ancestral symbiosis or evolved multiple times—broader large-scale phylogenomic studies will
482 be necessary.

483

484 **Perspectives and Challenges**

485 Genomic studies in legumes offer unprecedented opportunities to address fundamental
486 questions about plant evolution, crop domestication, and symbiotic interactions, but they also
487 present significant challenges. The availability of hundreds of reference genomes, especially in

488 Papilionoideae, has facilitated comparative genomics, shedding light on events such as whole-
489 genome duplications, genome fractionation, and the evolution of nodulation. However, the
490 genomic landscape of legumes remains uneven: while major crops and model plants as soybean,
491 common bean and *M. truncatula* have high-quality chromosome-scale assemblies, most
492 subfamilies—such as Cercidoideae, Detarioideae, Dialioideae, and the monospecific
493 Duparquetioideae—are still underrepresented or lack genomic resources altogether. This
494 imbalance limits broader phylogenomic insights and hampers the reconstruction of ancestral
495 genomes that reflect the evolution of the family.

496 Another challenge is the genome size variation, ranging from compact genomes to massive
497 repeat-rich genomes such as pea and faba bean, which complicates sequencing and assembly
498 efforts. Furthermore, despite advances in long-read sequencing and the availability of telomere-
499 to-telomere assemblies, many published genomes still lack in-depth analyses and discussions
500 related to repeat organization, structural variation, polyploidization history, and genome evolution,
501 being restricted to the description of the assembly or catalogues of genes. Moving forward,
502 perspectives in legume genomics involve expanding genomic coverage across neglected
503 subfamilies, integrating comparative approaches to refine models of genome evolution, exploring
504 the non-genic landscape, and leveraging pan-genomics and functional genomics to bridge
505 evolutionary biology with applied breeding. These efforts will be crucial not only to solve long-
506 standing evolutionary questions, such as the origin and loss of nodulation, but also to harness
507 legume diversity for sustainable agriculture.

508

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513

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753 **Figure legends**

754

755 **Figure 1.** Morphological diversity in Leguminosae. **(a–d)** *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*, **(b)** *Bauhinia*
756 *forficata*, **(c)** *Cenostigma nordestinum*, **(e)** *Leucaena leucocephala*, **(f)** *Albizia lebbeck*, **(g)** *Lotus*
757 *corniculatus*, **(h)** *Phaseolus coccineus*, **(i)** *Calliandra surinamensis*, **(j)** *Phaseolus lunatus*. **(k)**
758 Diversity of legume fruits (scale bar = 10 cm). **(l)** Typical seed organization within legume fruits.

759 **Figure 2.** Available genome assemblies at different scales across Leguminosae subfamilies.
760 Phylogenetic relationships are based on data from LPWG (2017), and divergence times follow
761 Zhao et al. (2021).

762 **Figure 3.** Phylogenetic relationships among Leguminosae subfamilies based on data from LPWG
763 (2017), indicating basic chromosome number and chromosome number variation according to Stai
764 *et al.* (2019). Flowers represent the morphological diversity of some representants of each
765 subfamily.

766 FIGURES

767

768 **Figure 1.** Morphological diversity in Leguminosae. (a–d) *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*, (b) *Bauhinia*
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